
COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL TREATMENT FOR IMPROVING DISTRESS IN PEDIATRIC ONCOLOGY: A PILOT STUDY

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to assess the psychological profile of oncology patients and to assess the effectiveness of a cognitive-behavioral treatment aimed to improve coping of pain and anxiety in childhood and youth cancer patients. The sample was of 12 patients, between 9 and 14 years diagnosed with cancer, to whom a protocol of psychological treatment was applied, with a duration of seven sessions that were carried out during the hospital admissions. There was a significant reduction in anxiety and an increase in positive affect levels. In individuals with high scores on the emotionality and extraversion scale, higher levels of post-treatment anxiety were found. These results provide evidence of the importance of applying treatments focused on treating the psycho-emotional effects in children with cancer.

Key words: *Oncology, Childhood, Distress, Cognitive-behavioral Treatment.*

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BACKGROUND

It is socially, clinically, and educationally known that the sequelae of childhood cancer involve a change in the lives of the children and their families on all levels. The patients must

readjust their routines (go to school, leisure and sports activities, family time, eating habits) to the demands and secondary effects of the medical treatment. However, this has not been entirely proven scientifically.

Along these lines, various studies have focused on studying the psycho-emotional effects of cancer and its treatment on children and their families, but they have found somewhat controversial results. Specifically, in specialized literature, studies that assess the psychological effects of childhood cancer can be grouped into two groups. In a first group, are those studies that support the fact that this alteration in the rhythm of child's life may involve difficulties in his self-concept (e.g., in adolescents due to the side effects of the treatment, such as the loss of hair, weight, and skin changes), social isolation, premature maturity, loss of concentration and irritability, depression, anxiety (Baggott, Cooper, Marina, Matthay, & Miaskowski, 2012;

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Çavuşoğlu, 2001; Eldad, 2009; Enskär et al., 2007; Hernández, López, & Durá, 2009; Kunin-Batson, Lu, Balsamo, Graber, & Devidas, 2016; Myers et al., 2014; Peterson et al., 2007), as well as an emotional and behavioral imbalance that increases the level of stress and affects the quality of life, both of the child and the family environment (Fernandez-Castillo & López-Naranjo, 2006; Glazebrook, Hollis, Heussler, Goodman, & Coates, 2003; Hysing, Elgen, Gillberg, & Lundervold, 2009; Roizen, Figueroa, Salvia, & Xia, 2007).

Along these same lines, it was found that these children show repertoires of avoidance and defense to cope reality and perceive their environment as threatening, generating a greater need for control and tolerance of stress, as well as feelings of vulnerability, anger, and difficulties with their peers (Buckner et al., 2014; Eldad, 2009; Rohayem et al., 2011).

Likewise, the impact and sequelae of childhood cancer are large since medical procedures are very invasive and long lasting, to the point that the pain from the disease itself is less than the pain evoked by cancer diagnostic and treatment procedures (Enskär et al., 2007).

Nevertheless, in the second group of studies, it was found that when children with cancer were compared with other children of their age with no health problems, the first had comparable levels or even lower anxiety and depression and higher self-esteem, as well as a more positive psychological adjustment (Essen, Enskär, Kreuger, Larsson, & Sjöden, 2000; Noll et al., 1999; Phipps, 2007).

Likewise, it has been observed that most adolescent cancer patients and survivors were no more distressed in terms of anxiety and depression, neither they present less self-esteem or greater psychosocial impairment than the general population; in fact, it has been found that the quality of life is increased in cancer patients who are cognitively and behaviorally involved in a healing and rehabilitation process and may be associated with a positive psychosocial adjustment (Bragado & Fernández, 1996; DeJong & Fombonne, 2006; Grootenhuis & Last, 2001; Zebrack et al., 2014). In view of these two divergent lines of results, some authors note that the differences between these two groups of studies are due to methodological differences (Bragado & Fernández, 1996; Myers et al., 2014), and they also note the stronger resilience of some patients who have less symptomatology (DeJong & Fombonne, 2006).

In turn, the need to consider personality assessment is evidenced in the literature; in

fact, different studies have shown (Dresch, 2007; Fierro & Cardenal, 2001) that the process of adaptation to the disease is mediated by the individual's own variables such as personality traits, since there is a close relationship between a normal personality as an indicator of physical and psychological health (Sanchez, García, Valverde, & Pérez, 2014), indicating better health states with the most adaptive polarities of the instruments that measure them (Millon, 2001). It is important to determine if certain behavioral tendencies such as much more rigid and less-adaptive behaviors will have some type of negative influence in the process of coping of the disease in the child and youth population. Likewise, it is considered important to have a measure of affect (trait) of children and adolescents, since the relationship of the affect with different areas of people's functioning in relation to health has been demonstrated (Taylor, Davis, & Zautra, 2013). Thus, while the positive affect (PA) would be a protective element, the negative affect (NA) would act as a risk factor for diseases (Krijthe, Walter, Hofman, Hunink, & Tiemeier, 2011).

The main psychological procedures currently applied for coping with the pain and anxiety of the invasive medical treatments follow a cognitive-behavioral conceptual and technical framework. In fact, a meta-analysis in which 22 studies were reviewed to see the effect of this therapy in children and adolescents with anxiety, depression, and somatic complaints showed a relatively large effect (0.74) compared to the group of children without treatment or with a placebo (Grossman & Hughes, 1992). Likewise, regarding the effectiveness of the treatments, the meta-analysis conducted by Samson and his team (Sansom-Daly, Peate, Wakefield, Bryant, & Cohn, 2012) where 25 studies were reviewed showed that interventions that were focused on non-directive emotional support by peers showed no significant results, and those that only followed an educational model of the disease and treatment showed a small improvement. As for the treatments that had a psycho-educational approach (information about the disease and management of distress), they differed greatly in their effects (fluctuating between small and large improvements). Regarding the interventions that used the computer as a mediating tool, they showed greater effects than the other interventions. Interventions based on coping and adaptation skills training (cognitive-behavioral techniques such as cognitive restructuring, problem-solving, role-playing games, etc.), through a minimum of four sessions, showed very high media effectiveness levels. As for the studies that included families

in the intervention, they showed significant results to a greater extent than those that did not include it. In summary, this meta-analysis indicates that the data found are inconclusive. Most studies show some positive effect in some post-treatment psychological measures, but with methodological limitations and no robust conclusions (Sansom-Daly et al., 2012). It is important to highlight that the application of psychological treatments in pediatric oncology, according to research (Landier & Tse, 2010; Méndez, Orgilés, López-Roig, & Espada, 2004), shows as decisive the psychological support for coping with the disease, making patients suffer less deterioration and increase the quality of life or, where appropriate, assimilate the loss of the child by family members.

In this study, a treatment with a cognitive behavioral approach was applied, which has demonstrated its effectiveness in this population (Seitz et al., 2014); it was also performed during the hospital admissions, which has highlighted the fact of being able to work with patients in the context where the main stressful events associated with the disease occur (painful medical treatments, long periods of hospitalization, isolation from their natural environment, among others), which is an advantage for treatment in two aspects: on the one hand, the therapist can evaluate and intervene in the patient's symptoms at the same time they occur, and on the other hand, the patient can implement the techniques and procedures psychologically that will be learned during the intervention in the real context, which will facilitate the generalization and practice of skills.

In view of all of the above, this work has two objectives. First, to evaluate and know the main psychological characteristics of hospitalized child and youth cancer patients, such as personality traits and syndromes, that indicate possible difficulties at the psychopathological level (withdrawal, somatic complaints, depression, among others), as well as assess the initial levels of pain and anxiety. Second, to evaluate the viability of a cognitive-behavioral treatment in a pilot trial aimed at improving the possible sequelae of cancer such as anxiety, pain, and affective problems in this population.

It is expected that there is a correlation between personality traits and variables that indicate some type of psychopathology, with levels of anxiety and pain. On the other hand, the intervention will improve coping with pain and anxiety evoked by the medical procedures to which these patients are subjected, as in the case of affection measures, it will increase the positive affect and decrease the negative.

METHOD

Participants

The sample was originally made up of 30 pediatric oncology patients who were hospitalized (for a period of 3 days or more) or in the day hospital (attending the hospital for treatment and returning home on the same day), with ages between 9 and 15 years with an average of 11 (SD = 2.8) years; however, for different reasons as shown in Figure 1, the sample for the analysis of the profiles was reduced to 12 patients, 7 boys and 5 girls. In turn, the analysis of the effectiveness of the treatment was performed with a final sample of nine patients with a mean age of 13 (SD = 1.4) years, 58% men and 42% women. The loss of three patients from the initial sample is due to the age of one of the patients in which all the variables of the study could not be analyzed (because there are no measuring instruments sensitive to their age) and two patients who they did not finish the treatment, one due to poor hospital assistance and another due to saturation of professionals intervening with him. Age, gender, and type of diagnosis per patient can be seen in Table 1.

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) being an oncological or hematological patient, which was verified from the medical diagnosis of the hospital team; (2) ages between 7 and 18 years, (3) score with an intelligence coefficient greater

Figure 1. Sample distribution – flow diagram

Table 1. Age, gender and diagnosis of patients who started treatment

Patient	Age	Gender	Diagnosis
1	5	Female	Lymphoblastic leukemia
2	13	Female	Lymphoblastic leukemia
3	13	Female	Ovarian tumor
4	13	Male	Lymphoblastic leukemia
5	8	Female	Spinal aplasia
6	13	Male	Lymphoblastic leukemia
7	10	Female	Lymphoblastic leukemia
8	13	Male	Lymphoblastic leukemia
9	14	Male	Facial tumor
10	14	Male	Lymphoblastic leukemia
11	9	Male	Neurofibromatosis
12	15	Male	Lymphoblastic leukemia

than 40 points from the previous psychological evaluation of the psychologist specialized in psychoncology of the team; and (4) absence of diagnosis of brain tumor with neurological condition, which was confirmed by the hospital's medical team.

Instruments

The instruments that allowed the evaluation of psychological and personality profiles, directly related to the achievement of the first objective of this work, are described below.

Eysenck Personality Questionnaire–Junior (EPQ-J): This assesses through a self-report three basic personality dimensions (neuroticism, extraversion-introversion, and psychoticism or tough-mindedness). It has two scales that measure sincerity and proneness to antisocial behavior. It is comprised of 81 yes/no items. The age range for its application is 8 to 15 years. The questionnaire has a reliability of 0.60 or even 0.70 in older subjects (Eysenck & Eysenck, 1997).

Child Behavior Check List (CBCL): The questionnaire allows assessing possible behavioral or emotional problems of patients. It consists of 120 items that parents respond by assessing different behaviors of their child, on a 3-point Likert scale: choosing 0 when its content is not true or is not relevant, 1 when it is something true or it happens sometimes, and 2 when it is very true and happens frequently; according to their age ranges, there is a questionnaire between 1 ½ and 5 years and another for 6–18 years. It evaluates eight syndromes: withdrawal, somatic complaints, anxiety/depression, social problems, thinking disorders, attention problems, offending behavior, and aggressive behavior. It has a Cronbach's alpha from 0.75 to 0.91 (Achenbach & Rescorla, 2001).

Youth Self Report (YSR): It was applied in patients who reached the age to complete this self-report, that is, being the age range of 11 to 18 years.

It consists of 105 items that value the same eight syndromes as the scale for the parents and with the same Likert type response format of three points. The scale's reliability has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.67 to 0.83 (Achenbach, 1991).

For the preliminary assessment of the effectiveness of the intervention directly related to the second objective, the following were used:

For pain perception (1), the Adolescent Pediatric Pain Tool (APPT) that assesses the location of pain based on marks in a body contour drawing. And (2) a pain intensity score measured by a *Visual Analog Scale (VAS)*; that is, a line of 10 centimeters that is divided between no pain (1), little (2), medium (3), large (4), and the worst possible pain (5), and quality descriptors for pain. Because the interest of this research was to know the intensity of pain, the VAS measure included in this instrument was taken as a reference for the interpretation of the data. The age of application includes between 5 and 18 years, and as psychometric goodness, it has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.81 (Jacob, Mack, Savedra, Van Cleve, & Wilkie, 2014).

In order to assess the effects on anxiety levels, the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory for Children (STAIC) was used. This instrument measures anxiety in two aspects: state, which refers to anxiety in a specific situation, and trait, at a general level as a more constant characteristic. It consists of 40 elements, 20 for each of the subscales. It is used for evaluation in adolescents between 9 and 15 years of age. It has a Cronbach's alpha between 0.83 and 0.92 (Spielberger, Gorsuch, & Lushene, 1982).

To assess the levels of anxiety and self-perceived pain before and after each session, a format was designed in which using a Likert scale from 0 (nothing) to 10 (a lot), the patient had to determine if he had pain or anxiety and in what grade. In the case of younger children, the parents or the researcher helped the child determine this score.

On the other hand, the Positive and Negative Affective Scale (PANAS) that measures PA was used to assess the effects at the emotional level of the intervention, that is, it represents the dimension of positive emotionality, energy, affiliation, and mastery of An individual, and NA, which refers to the dimension of temperamental sensitivity of an individual to negative stimuli. It consists of 20 items. Ten evaluate the PA (e.g., "I am a lively person, I get excited"), and another 10 evaluate the NA (e.g., "I feel nervous"). The questionnaire is completed by the child/adolescent taking into account how he/she feels and/or regularly behaves, following a scale of three response alternatives, described as "Never" (1), "Sometimes" (2), and

“Many times” (3). The scale has a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.70 and was validated in a population with an age range between 7 and 17 years (Sandín, 2003).

Design

The study was a controlled A-B-A-type clinical experiment with intra-subject replication. After taking baseline data (A), the psychological intervention was carried out in seven sessions (B), and outcome data were recorded at the end of treatment (A).

Procedure

A psychological treatment with cognitive-behavioral foundation is followed for coping with pain and anxiety. In this approach, the behavioral component aims to modify the child’s behaviors that establish, maintain, or increase pain; and the

cognitive component aims to allow children to focus on certain images or thoughts that allow them not to attend to pain sensations in its usual intensity because of selective concentration blocks or decreases painful perception by activating endogenous pain suppression systems (Salas et al., 2003).

Thus, after checking the inclusion criteria, obtain the affirmative diagnosis of cancer—with the absence of a brain tumor with a neurological condition—by the medical team, confirm their age and obtain informed consent from the parents, and obtain the data of the IC of the patient thanks to the collaboration of the hospital’s psycho-oncologist, the treatment protocol is started (starting with the pretest measurement of the profiles and the change variables) following the sequence indicated in Table 2. The treatment is performed individually

Table 2. Cognitive-behavioral pain and anxiety treatment protocol

Session	Purpose	Content
1	Take pretest data	The following instruments are applied to determine the baseline of each patient: APPT, PANAS, STAIC, EPQ-J, and YSR in the case of adolescents. If the patient is tired or does not wish to continue, the pretest is done in two sessions. In the first session of the pretest, the CBCL and CEEP are given to the parents so that they can answer them and be returned to the investigator in the next session with their child.
2	Promote the child’s participation in the treatment and therapeutic alliance Train in breathing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities for strengthening the therapeutic relationship or alliance: In the case of children, the therapist presented and offered game options (puzzles, coloring, or games that had the pediatric oncology area) or free play according to the interests of the child. In the case of adolescents, after the presentation of the therapist, they were encouraged to express their expectations and concerns about the intervention. • Application pre-session self-reports. • Then the work booklet was delivered, the presentation of the treatment was made and the patient was encouraged to ask the questions that he considered relevant. • Explanation of anxiety, pain and distress with the help of the support material that was in the workbook. • Train in breathing. • Application post session self-reports.
3	Train in relaxation techniques Continue practicing breathing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application pre-session self-reports. • In both children and adolescents, progressive muscle relaxation techniques were used. • Review previous contents. • Application post session self-reports.
4	Train in emotional education Continue practicing breathing and relaxation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application pre-session self-reports. • Recognition, expression and emotional control. • Review previous contents. • Application post session self-reports.
5	Train in imagination and distraction techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application pre-session self-reports. • For adolescents, the so-called imagination techniques were used: “empty the sandbag” and “the energy ball”. For the children the metaphor of “imagine that you are your favorite superhero” was used. • The distraction techniques were based on the particular tastes of the patients (painting, video games, reading ...) according to a list previously made in the session. • Review previous contents. • Application post session self-reports.
6	Train in behavioral test techniques Continue practicing previous components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application pre-session self-reports. • The behavioral test was carried out in two parts: in the first one through a role play, and in the second the patient had to apply what was learned in one of his chemotherapy sessions. • Post-session self-report application.
7	Acquire posttest data	The following instruments apply: APPT, PANAS, STAIC.

The techniques are described in detail in the treatment section.

and usually without the company of the parents (except when requested) in the room that each patient was assigned during their hospital admission. It was carried out by a licensed therapist and doctorate in psychology with experience in this type of treatment, over seven sessions, each with an approximate duration of 20 to 40 min (varies according to the technique to train and the child's disposition/Teen). Between the hospitalization cycles, that is, during the rest periods (minimum of 15 days), the patients practice the skills trained with the support of a booklet that allows them to review the strategies learned in the hospital with the therapists and encourage homework. The study has been approved by the ethical committee of the hospital where it was carried out.

Treatment

Next, the components and techniques of the treatment as a whole are specified as they were applied to the patients. The techniques are trained following the guidelines of the protocols and manuals validated in the Spanish population (Cautela & Groden, 1985; González-Maria, Fuentelsaz-Gallego, Moreno-Casbas, Gil-Rubio, & Herreros-López, 2013; Méndez, Orgiles, & Espada, 2008; Orgiles, Mendez, & Espada, 2009; Ortigosa, Mendez, & Riquelme, 2009) making the appropriate adaptations according to the motivation and the state of health that the patient presented in each session. Specifically:

1. *Breathing techniques*: Children are first taught to breathe slowly and deeply through instructions and modeling of the therapist, and then, the patient performs the behavior or practice test. The therapist corrects if there are errors in the performance of the technique by the child or verbally reinforces when it succeeds. With younger children, it starts with some games so that they become aware of their breathing (e.g., blowing bubbles, blowing up a balloon, etc.).
2. *Relaxation techniques*: When the children have mastered abdominal breathing, they go on to the relaxation stage. For the smallest children, the progressive or differential muscular relaxation procedure used is in the form of games, where they pretend to be different animals, and it explains that they are going to do some fun exercises that will help them to make their body calmer. For adolescents, Jacobson's progressive or differential muscle relaxation is used, which attempts to teach them to relax through exercises in which they alternately tense and relax their various groups of muscle.
3. *Emotional education*: In order for children to learn and practice emotion regulation skills, a session is held where they are taught the basic emotions using a story adapted to their age and then asked to remember situations when they had felt these emotions, either during their treatment or in their life in general. In older children (over 9 years of age) and adolescents, they are asked for reflections on the possible emotional effect of their treatment; that is, that reflects whether it has helped them to grow or strengthen them personally.
4. *Imagination Techniques*: The child is asked to get comfortable and slowly take three deep breaths, and then the therapist guides them by voice through two stories which the child has to imagine in order to diminish the pain in specific places, become deeply relaxed, and palliate negative emotions.
5. *Distraction techniques*: The child is asked to make a list of things he likes to do and distract them when they are in the hospital (e.g., drawing, reading, video games, etc.), and they are encouraged to use them in those moments of boredom and/or sadness.
6. *Test of techniques learned*: Finally, children practice different techniques learned during treatment in situations when pain and anxiety are greater through two behavioral tests. In the first trial that is carried out through role-play, the patient is the one who plays the role of "therapist" and must teach his patient (who would be the therapist) how to practice several techniques in a chemotherapy session. In the second trial, the patient is exposed to a real chemotherapy session and must apply the different techniques learned during the treatment. In this trial, the therapist does not intervene unless the patient requests it.

Data analysis

First, in order to assess the personality and psychological profiles of the patients, a descriptive analysis of the results obtained for each of the instruments of the study that are analyzed from the direct scores, percentages, means, and typical deviation was performed.

Second, a statistical analysis was carried out on the median differences between the pretest and the post-test with the Wilcoxon nonparametric test. In addition, the effect size was analyzed through

Cohen's *d* (1988), in which small effect size was considered for a *d* of 0.2, moderate effect size for 0.5 and large effect size for 0.8. Likewise, to assess whether anxiety levels at the beginning of the intervention could affect the effectiveness of the treatment, the Wilcoxon test was performed by dividing the sample based on their anxiety scores (scores above and below the 70th percentile in the STAIC state anxiety scale). On the other hand, a descriptive analysis of the pre- and post-test changes in the participants was carried out through the Wilcoxon signed ranges test.

RESULTS

The results are described below in two blocks: the first referring to the main psychological features of the full sample of patients, and the second referred to the evaluation of treatment effectiveness.

Block 1. Description of the main psychological characteristics of the patients

As observed in Table 3, personality traits analyzed with the EPQ-J showed that 50% of the patients scored above the 75th percentile in

extroversion, 37.5% in tough-mindedness, 25% in sincerity, and 25% in antisocial behavior.

In relation to behavioral problems assessed with the CBCL scale, Table 3 shows that one of the patients had clinical scores on the internalizing and externalizing scales and total score, 27.7% of the patients showed clinical-level internalizing problems, and 27.7% had subclinical internalizing problems, which means that 54.5% of the patients had clinical or subclinical internalizing problems; 9% (*n* = 1) of the patients had externalizing problems, and 27.7% had total scores in the clinical or subclinical range.

On the other hand, YSR scores were in a normal range except for one case in the subclinical range of affective problems and one case in the subclinical range in somatic problems and behavior problems (see Table 3).

Regarding the *initial state* of pain, anxiety, and affect levels, 18% of the patients had symptoms of pain measured through the VAS, 27% of the patients showed state type anxiety and 18% of the patients showed anxiety as a trait measured by the STAIC. Regarding affective states evaluated with PANAS, it is found that 63.6% of patients show PA below average and NA above average (see Table 3).

Table 3. Scores on personality scales, psychopathology, anxiety states, pain, and initial emotion

	EPQ-J						CBCL (M)			CBCL (F)		YSR					VAS	STAIC		PANAS		
	N	E	P	S	AB	T	I	Ex	T	I	Ex	Af	An	So	At	Op	Be		A/S	A/T	POS	NEG
1	—	—	—	—	—	45	48	51	47	40	50	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	—	—	—	—
2	5	90	10	10	20	59	40	49	62	44	49	50	52	50	50	50	50	2	75	60	23	14
3	50	5	50	20	10	60	49	52	62	49	56	53	64	55	50	60	50	1	85	80	18	22
4	25	80	75	45	65	—	—	—	70	54	64	53	64	65	57	50	68	2	80	80	23	12
5	—	—	—	—	—	56	44	51	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	10	—	—	—	—
6	5	50	99	5	5	58	53	58	—	—	—	53	52	50	60	50	50	0	4	4	24	11
7	10	99	10	45	90	67	53	61	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	10	20	30	27	12
8	20	95	10	10	25	55	34	45	—	—	—	53	58	52	51	53	50	2	50	15	28	22
9	65	10	50	70	25	61	51	56	50	46	47	65	64	52	52	56	55	2	65	60	18	19
10	25	50	90	75	75	69	66	72	57	56	61	63	50	56	54	50	50	1	15	5	22	16
11	—	—	—	—	—	57	53	50	50	33	36	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	35	65	24	19
12	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	80	55	84	50	50	50	2	35	90	25	25

Note: N: Neuroticism; E: Extraversion; P: Psychoticism; S: Sincerity; AB: Antisocial behavior. T: Total score; I: Internalizing; Ex: Externalizing; Af: Affective problems; An: Anxiety problems; So: Somatic problems; At: Attention problems and hyperactivity; Op: Oppositional defiance; Be: Behavioral problems; VAS: Visual Analog Scale; A/S: State anxiety; A/T: Trait anxiety; POS: Positive affection; NEG: Negative affection.

Block 2. Analysis of treatment effectiveness

In the comparison of the median scores between the pretest and post-test, through the Wilcoxon non-parametric test (Table 4), statistically, significant differences are found in self-reported measures of anxiety ($Z = -2.371$; $p < 0.05$) and pain ($Z = 2.06$; $p < 0.05$). The effect size for the measure of self-reported anxiety was large, with a Cohen's d of 1.09, and was moderate for the measure of self-reported pain with a d of 0.69. In addition, a large effect size is found in the pre- and post-changes for the PANAS NA variables ($d = 0.82$). Taking into account the initial levels of anxiety in the STAIC, statistically, significant differences are found between pretest and post-test scores in patients who presented high levels of anxiety at the beginning of treatment ($Z = -2.023$; $p < 0.05$); however, no differences were found in the rest of the variables.

At the descriptive level, the results indicated in Table 5 show that in pain levels measured with VAS, 44% of patients reduce their score at the end of the intervention. That is, although in the pretest, 88.9% felt pain below the average (five points below), at the end of the treatment, the percentage without pain increased in 100% of cases.

Regarding anxiety measures obtained by the STAIC, 78% of the cases reduce their score for the state anxiety scale, while 56% of the cases reduce the score for the trait anxiety scale. Performing this analysis at the level of clinical percentiles in both state and trait anxiety with STAIC, scores are reduced to 22% (initially 33% for State Anxiety and 44.5% for Trait) of cases located in the 70th percentile when comparing pretest and post-test scores.

At this point, it is striking that 75% of patients who increased their anxiety levels either in state

anxiety or trait anxiety also scored above the 75th percentile in the personality trait of Emotionality and Extraversion.

Regarding self-reported levels of anxiety and pain, we found that 78% of cases perceive less

Table 4. Wilcoxon signed ranges test (n = 9)

		N	Average Range	Ranks Sum
VAS	Negative range	4	3	12
	Positive range	2	4.5	9
	Tie	3		
	Total	9		
STAIC	Negative range	7	4.29	30
	Positive range	2	7.5	15
A/S	Tie	0		
	Total	9		
STAIC	Negative range	5	6	30
	Positive range	4	3.75	15
	Tie	0		
A/T	Total	9		
	Negative range	7	4	28
	Positive range	0	0	0
	Tie	2		
ANXIETY	Total	9		
	Negative range	5	3	15
	Positive range	0	0	0
PAIN	Tie	4		
	Total	9		
	Negative range	1	4	4
	Positive range	4	2.75	11
AF +	Tie	1		
	Total	6		
PANAS	Negative range	4	3.25	13
	Positive range	1	2	2
	Tie	1		
AF -	Total	6		

Table 5. Direct scores, mean, median, and standard deviation of dependent variables

	VAS		STAIC A/S		STAIC A/T		Self-report anxiety		Self-reporting pain		PANAS (Positive affection)		PANAS (Negative affection)	
	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	PRE	POST
1	2	5	75	20	60	4	5	2	7	2	23	—	14	—
2	1	4	85	77	80	89	6	5	5	5	18	—	22	—
3	2	0	80	45	80	5	5	3	1	0	23	—	12	—
4	0	0	4	40	4	35	1	1	0	0	24	26	11	17
5	10	2	20	70	30	35	10	2	10	2	27	27	12	12
6	2	1	50	25	15	20	10	1	2	1	28	24	22	13
7	2	2	65	55	60	20	0	0	2	2	18	23	19	11
8	1	1	15	4	5	4	1	0	1	1	22	25	16	12
9	2	1	35	10	90	75	4	0	2	1	25	27	25	18
Mean	2.44	1.77	47.66	38.44	41.11	31.88	4.66	1.55	3.33	1.55	23.11	25.33	17	13.83
Median	2	1	50	40	60	20	5	1	2	1	24	25.5	17.5	12.5
SD	2.92	1.71	30.39	25.78	34.07	31.02	3.67	1.66	3.31	1.5	3.48	1.63	5.17	2.92
Z	0.316		0.889		0.889		2.371		2.06		0.948		1.483	
P	0.72		0.374		0.374		0.018		0.039		0.343		0.138	
d	0.28		0.32		0.28		1.09		0.69		0.48		0.82	

anxiety, and 56% report perceiving less pain at the end of the intervention.

On the other hand, in the PANAS score, we found that 67% of the participants increase their PA score, and 67% reduce their NA score at the end of the intervention. In an analysis of changes in relation to the average score in the normative population of the instrument, it was found that the PA score for 77.8% of the patients that was below the average in the pretest score ($M = 23.11$; $SD = 3.48$) increases 2.22 points in the post-test score ($M = 25.33$; $SD = 1.63$).

Regarding the NA, for 66.7% of the patients, the pretest score was below the average ($M = 17$; $SD = 5.17$), increasing the post-test score in 100% of the cases ($M = 13.83$; $SD = 2.92$); that is, all patients have improved their NA scores below the average.

Finally, continuing with treatment effectiveness, Figure 2 shows the falling trend of medians on the VAS, STAIC State Anxiety, STAIC Trait Anxiety, and self-reported anxiety scales.

In the same figure, a rising trend in PA on the PANAS and stable level of self-reported pain may be observed.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of an intervention protocol with

different components for coping with pain and anxiety in pediatric onco-hematology. This was a pilot study, which produced preliminary data. The results clearly show its effectiveness for significantly lowering anxiety, considering that from the beginning of treatment, there is little pain. These results of our study are in agreement with what has been reported on the positive effect of cognitive-behavioral therapy in distress symptom management (Sansom-Daly et al., 2012). Furthermore, patients reported a positive impact of techniques learned and that they had included them in other aspects of their lives; for example, they practiced relaxation and breathing techniques when they had a hard time sleeping or for pain caused by something other than the treatment. This coincides with Bellver's study (cited by Pérez & Martínez, 2015), which mentions how adolescents with cancer responded positively to cognitive-behavioral skills and techniques, incorporating these skills in their daily lives.

On the other side, the need to explore and treat psycho-emotional factors in long-term hospitalized patients was also confirmed. At the beginning of treatment, most of the patients had scores below the mean in PA, which diminished considerably at the end of the treatment, and the percentage of patients with PA above the mean increased.

Figure 2. Median punctuation of patients

The same thing happened with the scores in NA, which at the end of treatment had gone down to below the mean in all the patients.

These data coincide with those suggested by Méndez, Orgiles, López-Roig, and Espada (2004) on the fact that physical and emotional repercussions of illness, as well as secondary effects of treatments used to coping with cancer, can be reduced with proper psychological intervention; likewise, the importance of family and social/healthcare psychological support is presented as fundamental for the child to feel psychologically and emotionally better and also as a protective factor (Haase, 2004).

Although the data are preliminary and the number of participants, for now, does not allow more powerful statistical analysis to determine a clear relationship between the main psychological characteristics of patients and their levels of pain, anxiety, and mood, with respect to styles of personality draws attention that patients who raised their levels of post-treatment anxiety, also presented higher scores on the Emotionality and Extraversion scale, which defines a subject who scores high on this scale as anxious, worried, with changes in humor, and often depressed, with high emotion and very strong reactions to all kinds of stimuli, it is also difficult to return to the normality of each experience.

However, there are some methodological limitations of the study, such as the need to take baseline measurements over a longer time or propose a study with multiple baselines. Likewise, although the assessment instruments are adapted to the child and youth population, some problems of understanding the items have been found. Likewise, having a small sample has limited the possibility of performing a more powerful statistical analysis that allows drawing stronger conclusions regarding the efficacy of the treatment, so it is expected to continue enlarging the sample of patients for future studies and also use control groups (a waiting list).

Regarding the difficulties that arose during the implementation of the treatment program in the hospital context, we highlight the following: (1) The patient's own health, since his condition depended on the medical procedures to which he was subjected during his admissions (chemotherapy application, invasive tests, side effects such as vomiting and dizziness, isolation by lowering defenses, among others). So even if there was a schedule of the psychological treatment sessions, if the patient was not physically well, they should be postponed, in order to always prioritize the patient's physical health. (2) The patient refused to receive psychological treatment, which usually occurred when a

medical complication had arisen, and the patient refused to receive psychological treatment until he was "a little better" emotionally. (3) For parents, the process of coping with their child's illness was suffered, in fact sometimes they rejected psychological treatment for their children, even after explaining the advantages it could represent, Some of them under the justifications of "not overloading their child" or "saturating him/her with more treatments", or "not having themselves to answer more questions about their child's health".

Among the limitations of clinical application, we found that in most cases the psychological intervention had to be applied in widely spaced sessions, which required review sessions. It should also be noted that they served as an enriching process for the patient and as a useful tool for the therapist since the complications that the patients could have suffered or their refusal to participate in a particular session were worked during the subsequent therapy sessions and they were included as experiences that the patient learned to work and face in a more functional way when they happened again.

In sum, this work provides evidence on the psychological characteristics of pain and anxiety in hospitalized patients, as well as deepening the need to include and consider psycho-emotional aspects of the intervention. In addition, it provides a specific intervention protocol in this population.

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